

ISic3098

I.Sicily inscription 3098

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331423

1. [— — — — — — — — —]
2. ΓΗΠ Α,Ο [— — — — — ὑπατία]
3. τοῦ δεσπ[ότου ἡμῶν Θεο]-
4. δοσίου [τὸ —' κ(αὶ) — —]
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645446

PHI 331423

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 36.0870

Ferrua, A 1982-1983. Le iscrizioni datate della Sicilia paleocristiana. *Kokalos*. 28-29: 3-29. At 12 no.32
undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 389

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